

ABSTRACT

RADIOIMAGING ALGORITHM IN THE DIAGNOSIS OF THE DIVERTICULA OF THE COLON

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Background. Diverticulosis affects around 30% of the population over 60 years old. This is one of the most significant diseases of the gastrointestinal diseases both clinically and economically. Hence, sufficient radiological evaluation of diverticulitis and its complications is of vital importance in determining the proper medical and surgical treatment for these patients.

Objective of the study. To determine the radio-imaging algorithms in the diagnosis of the diverticula of the colon. **Material and methods.** The study presents a retrospective analysis of clinical and radiological data of 78 patients suspected for colon diverticula disease hospitalized in the radiological department Municipal Clinic Hospital "St. Trinity" from September to December 2024. There were 27 Women (35%) and 51 Men (65%), aged between 20 and 80. Based on the gathered information, all 78 patients (100%) passed the simple abdominal radiography, 19 patients for barium enema, 5 patients for MRI, 66 patients for CT. With the help of my associate doctor, we conducted a thorough examination of each patient's condition. Our analysis was greatly aided by a specialized table designed to differentiate between different imaging diagnostic algorithm in colon diverticular disease. Plain X-Ray, Barium enema, CT scan, MRI, Colonoscopy, Ultrasound. **Results.** The relationship between clinical and imaging diagnosis of colonic Diverticula pathology is one of the most important criteria for the differential diagnosis and follow up strategy. In our study, patient's complains included: Abdominal pain (46%), Constipation (93%), Fever (29%), tenderness (49%), bleeding (22%) and signs of infection (26%) and treatment results: positive follow-up 78% and Negative follow-up 22%. **Conclusion.** The integration of clinical symptoms with radiological findings plays a fundamental role in the differential diagnosis of diverticula of the colon. While Simple Abdominal Radiography made in 100% of our patients, can provide a quick and initial assessment more about complications of colonic diverticula, Abdominal and pelvic CT imaging made in 85% of our patients, offers superior details, including and detecting several other

pathologies like Liver steatosis, Liver lesions, Chronic Pancreatitis, Renal stones, Renal lesions, Prostate hyperplasia and Uterus lesions.

Key words: Diverticula, Radiology, Computer tomography, Ultrasound, MRI.